

Impact of Internet on Growth of E-Commerce

Industry

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ABSTRACT

E-commerce has transformed the way business is done in India and the world. The E-commerce sector has brought a paradigm shift in the trading business. The revolution in technology has enabled the industry to grow faster. The increased online user base and smartphone penetration has led to an impressive growth in the last few years. India's rising internet accessibility and demographic dividend contribute to the growth of e-commerce industry.

This research paper presents the effect of mobile subscriptions and internet on the growth of e-commerce industry in India. It also tries to evaluate the preferred modes of payment by consumers. The researcher has used secondary data from various journals and websites. Quantitative research has been used to analyze data and conclusions are drawn via multivariate correlation co-efficient. From the study it is evident that with the growth in usage of internet and smart phones, customers are switching to online buying and selling. As India is a young country and since youngsters use online method of shopping, hence e-commerce industry in India is growing at a faster rate. Males prefer to buy online more than offline whereas females tend to buy using the traditional method more. Therefore electronic goods constitute a major chunk of online purchases. M-wallet is the most preferred mode of payment.

Keywords: E-Commerce, Internet, Smart phone, M-wallet, Online Banking, Cash On Delivery(COD), Credit Card

Introduction:

E-commerce has transformed the way business is done in India and the world. The E-commerce sector has brought a paradigm shift in the trading business. Hence this industry has tremendous growth opportunities. Due to e-commerce it is possible to access goods from all over the world. The revolution in technology has enabled the industry to grow faster. The increased online user base and smart phone penetration has led to an impressive growth in the last few years. India's rising internet accessibility and demographic dividend contribute to the growth of e-commerce industry. The digital transformation is expected to increase India's total internet user base to 829 million by 2021 from 636.73 million in FY19. India's e-commerce revenue has grown at an annual rate of 51 percent from 2017 to 2020, the highest in the world. With the increase in internet user base, e-commerce in India is also growing steadily.

Propelled by launch of 4G networks, increasing consumer wealth and increasing smart phone penetration, the e-commerce market in India is expected to grow to US\$200 billion by 2026 from US\$38.5 billion in 2017. During 2018, electronics was the biggest contributor to online retail sales in India with a share of 48 per cent.

I. Research Objective:

1. To analyze the effect of mobile subscriptions and internet on the growth of E-commerce industry in India
2. To evaluate the preferred payment mode by users for E-commerce in India

II. Research Methodology:

The researcher has used secondary data from various journals, websites and articles. Data has been collected from websites and proper references are given wherever necessary. Quantitative research has been used to analyze data obtained from websites for the period 2009 to 2018. Statistical methods such as multivariate correlation coefficient are used to analyze the effect of internet and mobile telephone subscriptions on the growth of e-commerce in India. The various payment modes are observed from 2017 to 2019.

III. Literature Review:

Abhijit Mitra (2013) in his paper "E-commerce In India- A Review" has mentioned that there are websites or applications which offer a specific product and other allied services. It is easy to expand physical business via internet, it is growing at a higher rate with the increase in usage of internet. This paper identifies Payment collection, logistics, vendor management, taxation, etc as barriers of e-commerce. According to Sarode R.M. (2015) there is vast scope for e-commerce in India as only 19% population is buying online. There is a need for proper legal framework in India so that online trade can expand horizons and consumer protection is taken care of. Internet users are increasing in both urban and rural areas. E-commerce players in India face challenges such as cyber security, regulatory structure, organization scaling, payment transactions, digital experience, compliance framework and market strategy.

According to Sarbapriya Ray (2011) the major opportunities identified are global trade, lower search costs and increased power of downstream players. Dr Kishor Kumar Das and Affreen Ara (2015) have focused on the impact of e-commerce such as changes in living standards of people, increasing use of smartphones and computers along with Internet. Madhurima Khalsa and Harish Kumar (2017) provide an insight into E-commerce business which has shown tremendous growth in the recent years due to increased consumer awareness, investor trust and technological proliferation. They suggest that e-commerce should exist as complementary to traditional business. Nisha Chanana and Sangeeta Goele (2012) have said that factors such as replacement guarantee, M-Commerce services, location based services, multiple payment option, product quality, dedicated 24/7 customer care centre will significantly contribute to the boom of the E-Commerce industry in India. Dr. Rajasekar, S. and Sweta Agarwal (2016) in their research paper have stated the various modes of payment. A major challenge faced by the industry is that high speed internet is not available to most citizens of nation at affordable rates.

Kalia P, Kaur N. & Singh T. (2017) explain that the Global Retail E-Commerce Index is based on metrics such as online market size, technology adoption and consumer behavior, infrastructure and growth potential. The

constraints which India faces are poor internet penetration, infrastructure, low credit card penetration, complex tax laws and paucity of funds. According to Dr. Shettar R.M.(2016), due to E-commerce the existence of wholesalers is at risk because the producer can easily ignore them and sell their products to the retailers and the consumers. It has impacted on how we communicate, travel and access available information for trading of goods and services.

V The E-Commerce Industry

B2B (Business to Business):

In the world of e-commerce B2B includes all transactions that take place between two business organizations. Every exchange that involves business at both the end is considered such as manufacturing industries and dealers, wholesalers and retailers. B2B e-commerce has the highest growth rates among all other segments and it occupies almost 80% of e-commerce. B2B includes activities like procurement, supplier management, inventory management, channel management, sales activities, payment management, and service and support. For example, Indiamart.com.

B2C (Business to Consumers):

Direct commercial transactions between businesses and consumers are termed as B2C e-commerce. B2C involves gathering information by the customer about the product, making purchases of goods and services. B2C provides several advantages to the consumers as they find it more convenient, time saving, easy for comparison, provide feedback about the product, availability of lot of options and lower prices than the traditional business. It reduces the transaction costs of the consumers as they do the research before purchasing and buy the product at the most appropriate prices available according to them. B2C e-commerce includes online travel, online retail, online classifieds, digital downloads and financial services. Online travel holds 71% of the B2C market and the retail is growing with 16% of this market. Myntra.com, Flipkart.com, Jabong.com are few of the leading online retailers.

C2C (Customer to Customer):

This type of e-commerce includes the transactions that are made between two or more consumers, where a consumer sells goods and services to another consumer. This is significantly very less portion of the e-commerce industry. In this an online portal connects two consumers, one who wants to sell and the others who wants to buy. These are the transactions between two private individuals over an online portal. This has become a totally new market place, which provides new market places and online auctions of products and services. A particular buyer can choose between various sellers for that one particular good. For example, eBay.in.

Growth of E-Commerce Sector:

The growth in e-commerce sector is propelled by the increased penetration of smart phones and access to internet especially in the urban areas. Online orders are increasing due to E-wallets, cash on delivery method of payment, discounts offered by market players, faster deliveries and access to a variety of products. A particular category of goods such as smart phones sell online more than offline, whereas electronic appliances and fashion products such as apparel and shoes perform more as a supplementary channel.

Source: IBEF Report, Dec 2019

Since 2014 there has been a remarkable growth in e-commerce sales. From 14 US\$ billion in 2014 it has reached 50 US\$ billion in 2018. Currently there are 1-1.2 million transactions per day in e-commerce retailing.

Source: eMarketer, May 2019

It can be clearly observed that the growth in ecommerce sales from 2018 to 2019 is the highest in India and China amongst the top 10 countries in ecommerce sales. In global comparison, India ranks ninth in ecommerce revenue in 2019.

Source: IBEF Report, Dec 2019

Electronic goods such as smartphones comprise 48% of the total e-commerce sales. Apparels constitute 29% whereas home and furnishing, personal care products and books constitute the remaining 23% of the total sales in e-commerce.

Analysis:

Year	Retail E-commerce sales (Billion US\$)	% of individuals using internet	% of mobile telephone subscriptions
2009	3.9	5.12	45
2010	5.1	7.5	64
2011	6.3	10.07	75
2012	11.4	12.58	71
2013	13	15.1	72
2014	14	21	76
2015	20	17	80
2016	30	22	89
2017	39	34.45	91
2018	50	35	93

Source: ITU indicators database, IBEF Report

Multivariate Correlation Co-efficient			
	Retail E-commerce sales (Billion US\$)	% of individuals using internet	% of mobile telephone subscriptions
Retail E-commerce sales (Billion US\$)	1		
% of individuals using internet	0.954570929	1	
% of mobile telephone subscriptions	0.839477746	0.867349803	1

From the analysis it is evident that the correlation co-efficient with internet is 0.95 and with mobile phones is

0.83. Thus e-commerce sales are very highly positively correlated to individuals using internet and mobile subscriptions. As the reach of internet increases, ecommerce sales increase. It also increases with increase in sales of smart phones as it is very convenient to buy or sell goods and services through mobile phones. Ecommerce sales are also proportional to users of internet by age, gender and income.

Source: Statista Global Consumer Survey, October 2019

Individuals from age group 25-34 years use internet maximum i.e. 37.40% whereas youngsters also use it a lot, individuals above 45 years use internet the least.

Source: Statista Global Consumer Survey, October 2019

In India, males use internet more than females. This explains the phenomenon that electronic goods are sold more through the online mode.

Source: Statista Global Consumer Survey, October 2019

The chart depicts that individuals earning high income buy online more. The low income group also does

online buying. There is not much difference amongst buyers from different income groups. This means that irrespective of income people are using internet for trading of goods and services.

Source: Statista, January 2020

It can be observed that payments made through M Wallet are increasing and currently constitute the most preferred mode for online purchases (43%). People do prefer (Cash on Delivery) COD mode (30% in 2019) as well. Online Banking involves online transfer of funds through NEFT and RTGS. There is not much variation in usage of online banking and card (debit card and credit card) payments over the period.

VI. Findings and Conclusions:

From the analysis it is evident that the correlation co-efficient of e-commerce sales with internet is 0.95 and with mobile phones is 0.83. Thus e-commerce sales are very highly positively correlated to individuals using internet and mobile subscriptions. As the reach of internet increases, ecommerce sales increase. It also increases with increase in sales of smart phones as it is very convenient to buy or sell goods and services through mobile phones. Ecommerce sales are also proportional to users of internet by age, gender and income. Individuals above 18 years upto 35 years use maximum internet and since India is a young country the e-commerce industry has a lot of scope to expand. Since men use internet more than women electronic goods are traded more on the e-commerce platform. There is not much difference amongst number of buyers from different income groups. This depicts that irrespective of income people are using internet for trading of goods and services.

It can be observed from the chart that payments made through M Wallet are increasing and currently constitute the most preferred mode for online purchases (43%). People do prefer (Cash on Delivery) COD mode as well. There is not much variation in usage of online banking and debit card and credit card payments.

VII. Limitations and Challenges:

The research has been done carried out using secondary data available. References have been mentioned wherever necessary. Since E-commerce is quite new in India data prior to 7 years was not available.

Although the e-commerce industry is growing at a very fast pace, there are many challenges faced by the industry in India. There are security issues faced by people while making payments. Access to speed internet facility, awareness and literacy regarding use of different modes of payment are some other issues involved. Improvement in these issues will lead to even higher growth in the e-commerce industry.

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